

Comparison of FTIR Spectra and Related Derivatized Spectra of Tablets Containing Levothyroxine Obtained ATR and With KBr Pellets

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Abstract

Thyroid hormones are biological molecules that play a critical role in regulating metabolic rate and maintaining many physiological functions of the organism. Lack of iodine leads to various endocrine disorders, especially hypothyroidism. Synthetic levothyroxine (LT4) is generally preferred in the medication of hypothyroidism. LT4 is a molecule with low water solubility and high thermosensitivity. Absorption of the drug varies depending on gastric pH, integrity of the gastrointestinal mucosa and concomitant medications. Levotiron tablet samples of 100 mg and 25 mg were used in this study. The powdered tablets were first analyzed directly in FTIR-ATR and then in FTIR using KBr. Spectra were obtained in the mid-infrared region ($4000-550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) with 64 scans and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The obtained spectra were peak analyzed with Origin Pro software. Savitzky-Golay smoothing and filtering method was applied during 2nd order differentiation to remove noise and background effects in the spectra. When the spectra of 25 mg samples prepared directly and with KBr pellet were examined, different intensities were found at the same peak positions. However, some peaks such as C-I appeared better in samples prepared with pellets. It is thought that derivatized spectra will support chemometric analysis in quantitative analysis studies.

Keywords: Levotiroksin (LT4), FTIR-ATR, savitzky-golay, derivatized spectra, FTIR-KBr

1. Introduction

Thyroid hormones are important hormones that regulate the metabolic rate and affect the functioning of many systems in the body (Azizi et al., 2025). These hormones are synthesized by the thyroid gland and act on many organs. The thyroid gland, the largest of the endocrine glands, secretes the hormones T3 (Triiodothyronine) and T4 (Thyroxine), which regulate the rate of human metabolism starting from the womb. Thyroid hormones regulate the function of almost every cell and tissue in the body (Öcal, 2015). Iodine is required for the production of thyroid hormones. The thyroid gland takes iodide ions from the blood and converts them into atomic iodine. Atomic iodine binds to tyrosine to form iodothyrosines, an iodinated amino acid derivative involved in the synthesis of thyroid hormones. This process is an important step in the synthesis of thyroid hormones (Köküner and Şehirli, 2015). Iodine deficiency in our body causes many diseases, especially thyroid diseases. The most common of these diseases are hypothyroidism and Hashimoto's disease. These diseases are the most common thyroid dysfunctions worldwide, characterized by a deficiency of thyroid hormones. Some medications and radiotherapy can also cause hypothyroidism. If not treated, this disease causes systemic damage and in advanced cases "myxedema coma" develops (Çakır et al., 2021). Today, various pharmaceutical preparations are used for the treatment of iodine deficiency. These pharmaceutical products include drugs with levothyroxine as an active pharmaceutical ingredient. Routine TSH monitoring and dose optimization are critical for treatment success in LT4 treatment (Candan and Yorulmaz, 2023). Levothyroxine (LT4) is a laboratory-produced synthetic drug used to correct a deficiency of thyroid hormone in the body. LT4 is a white crystalline powder with low solubility in ethanol and water (0.105 mg/mL at 25°C). However, levothyroxine shows high solubility (due to its low crystal lattice energy and high hydration energies) in dilute solutions of alkali hydroxides (Shaban, 2018). LT4 pKa values, carboxyl group (pKa1=2.4) phenolic group (pKa2=6.8) and

amino group (pKa3= 9.9) (Sreeramoju et al., 2021). In this study, the physicochemical and pharmacological properties of levothyroxine were investigated in detail. Levothyronine tablet samples of 100 mg and 50 mg were used in the study. The tablets were analyzed by FTIR-ATR in powder form and by FTIR using KBr pellet. In addition, peak analysis was performed on the obtained spectra with Origin Pro software and derivative spectra were evaluated.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Sample preparation

Levotiron 100 mg and levotiron 25 mg tablets obtained from twenty different local pharmacies were used in the study. Twenty tablets were used for each group and analyses were performed in three replicates. Each tablet contains 25 and 100 mg Levothyroxine sodium. Excipients specified in the drug package insert; Corn starch, magnesium stearate, lactose monohydrate FP (bovine milk), gelatin 80 bloom (bovine gelatin), croscarmellose sodium.

2.2. FTIR Analysis using KBr pellet

The tablet samples are thoroughly powdered with an agate mortar and pestle. The powdered samples are mixed 150 mg of dry potassium bromide (KBr) powder (KBr is IR-transparent and acts as a matrix). Then, the mixture is placed in a pellet mold. Pressure (25 Mpa) is applied using a hydraulic press to form a transparent and clear pellet. Finally, the KBr pellet is placed in the sample holder of the FTIR instrument for analysis. Spectra were collected from the Mid-IR (MIR) region between 400-4000 cm^{-1} with 64 scans and a scan resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . To ensure that there was no interference at the specified wave number, 150 mg KBr pellet prepared under the same conditions was scanned and blank readings were recorded.

2.3. FTIR-ATR analysis

Perkin Elmer Frontier FTIR-ATR spectroscopy was used in the study. The tablets were powdered at room temperature before analysis. Spectra were collected from the Mid-

IR (MIR) region between 550-4000 cm^{-1} with 64 scans and a scan resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Each analysis was taken in triplicate and averaged. Results are shown as percent transmittance (T%). Samples were analyzed at room temperature to minimize noise. After each analysis, the ZnSe diamond crystal was cleaned with ethyl alcohol and distilled water.

2.4. Peak analysis

The parameters used for peak analysis are as follows; the iteration algorithm is Levenberg Marquardt, the model is Gaussian and the number of anchors is 11. And also adjacent-Averaging smoothing was used. Other parameters were set as; smoothing window size 3, peak finding setting method is local maximum, local points is 2, peak filtering method is by height and threshold height 20%.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Physicochemical and pharmacological properties of levothyroxine

In the LT4 molecule, an oxygen atom located between two aromatic rings forms the aryl-ether bond, giving the molecule ether properties. The molecule contains a carboxylic acid (-COOH) group and a primary amine (-NH₂) group; these groups allow levothyroxine to exhibit both acidic and basic properties. The four iodine (I) atoms in its structure are covalently bonded to aromatic rings. This plays a fundamental role in the affinity of levothyroxine for thyroid receptors and its biological activity (Shaban, 2018). LT4 is an amphipathic molecule containing a hydrophilic alanyl side chain and a hydrophobic diphenyl ether core. Both aromatic rings in the molecule are planar and located almost at right angles to each other (Aleskandrany and Şahin, 2020).

Figure 1. Chemical structure of levothyroxine ((2S)-2-amino-3-[4-(4-hydroxy-3,5-diiodophenoxy)-3,5-diiodophenyl]propanoic acid).

Degradation of levothyroxine occurs by several pathways; deiodination, oxidation, deamination, decarboxylation, side chain branching and dimerization. LT4 is sensitive to heat. Therefore, the process of formulating LT4 can affect its chemical stability (Shaban, 2018). LT4 is also sensitive to various factors such as light, oxygen, humidity, temperature and pH (Chamelarocá et al., 2024). In the Raman spectroscopy study, the pure solid-state spectrum of LT4 was compared with the spectra of membrane complexes formed with phospholipids and the structural changes of the

molecule were determined. Furthermore, fluorescence spectroscopy techniques were used to demonstrate that LT4 hormones bind spontaneously, strongly and reversibly to lipid media (Aleskandrany and Şahin, 2020). The absorption of LT4 is affected by several factors (Liu et al., 2023). Some drugs affect the absorption of levothyroxine. May alter the pharmacokinetics of thyroid hormones in several ways. Drugs that reduce TSH release (dopamine, glucocorticoids, octreotide, rexinoids) lead to decreased thyroid hormone concentrations. Proton pump inhibitors such as

omeprazole and lansoprazole have also been evaluated with TSH levels in patients and shown to affect levothyroxine absorption. This is because normal gastric acid secretion plays an important role in thyroxine absorption. However, compared with other healthy individuals, famotide was found to have no such effect. These drugs make the absorption of levothyroxine more difficult by forming non-absorbable complexes or by binding in the intestine (Colucci et al., 2013). Chemical and physical incompatibilities between the active substance and excipients adversely affect the chemical structure, stability and bioavailability of the drug (Yılmaz, 2006). Therefore, it is critical to perform chemical and physical compatibility tests with analytical techniques such as HPLC (High pressure liquid chromatography), XRD (X-ray diffraction) and TGA (Thermogravimetric analysis) in the early stages of formulation studies (Pottel, 2020). Drug interactions affect pharmacokinetic processes. For example: administration of beta-blockers such as asebutilol, oxprenolol and timolol can lower T3 levels by altering the extracellular distribution of T3. Protein binding is also

involved in these interactions. The high rate of binding of levothyroxine to proteins may alter the effect of the drug. Some drugs such as salicylates, furosemide, heparin temporarily increase free T4 levels by decreasing the protein binding of levothyroxine (Colucci et al., 2013). LT4 is available in the form of tablets, soft gel capsules and solution. Soft gel and liquid formulations are used in patients with gastrointestinal disorders and reduced intestinal absorption of LT4 due to various factors. (Benvenga and Carlé, 2019; Capelli et al., 2025). The tablet form is the most commonly used formulation.

3.2. FTIR results

Data analysis was performed on averaged spectra. In all spectra, the spectrum wave number ranges were specifically evaluated, and characteristic regions and peaks were identified. The spectra obtained using FTIR-ATR and using KBr pellet are given in Figure 2. All of the spectra show peaks belonging to functional groups associated with the most important structural features (Ledeti et al., 2016).

Figure 2. Spectra of levotiron powder samples obtained by FTIR-ATR and using KBr pellet

The stretching vibration of the O-H bond from water gave a more extensive spectral peak in the range of 3500-3200 cm^{-1} in the spectra prepared with KBr pellet. The stretching vibration of the C-H bond originating from the methylene group and aromatic rings was observed at 2934, 2887 and 3053 cm^{-1} , respectively. The stretching vibration of the phenolic O-H bond was observed at 3531 cm^{-1} . N-H-induced peaks

between 3200-3500 cm^{-1} (3264, 3270, 3459 cm^{-1}) were determined by the presence of multiple bands overlapping with the O-H band. The peak at 1660 cm^{-1} belonging to the bending vibration of the second bonds and the peak at 1058-1084 cm^{-1} belonging to the stretching vibration of the C-N bond were observed. The functional groups of the peaks in the study are given in Table 1 (Ledet et al., 2020; AlBathish et al., 2024)

Table 1. Functional groups of the peaks in the study

Peak wavenumber (cm^{-1})	Functional groups
552	C-I
876 and 915	C-H bending vibrations of bonds (out-of-plane deformation)
1058	C-O (phenol)
1168	C-O vibration (ether), bending vibrations of C-H bonds
1262	C-O (acid)
1325	C-N bending
1359	C-N
1393	C=O symmetric stress
1456	stretching vibration of C=C bonds from aromatic systems
1470	C-H stretching vibration
1660	C=C

3.3. Comparison of derivative spectra

After Savitzky-Golay correction, the 2nd order derivative of the data point was calculated. All peaks of the 2nd order derivative curve were found by the “local maximum” method. The second derivated, Savitzky-Golay smoothing and filtering method help to gain visibility of fingerprint region 1000-400 cm^{-1} . The Savitzky-Golay technique was used to remove noise and

background effects from the spectra. In this way, overlapping peaks in the raw FTIR spectrum were distinguished. When the spectra of 25 mg samples prepared directly and with KBr pellet were examined, different intensities were found at the same peak positions. However, some peaks appeared better in the samples prepared with pellets; for example the C-I peak. Derivative spectra of 25 mg. samples, prepared powder and using KBr pellets are given in Figure 3 and 4.

Figure 3. Derivative spectra of 25 mg samples, prepared powder.

Figure 4. Derivative spectra of 25 mg samples, prepared using KBr pellets

In the derivative spectra of the samples prepared with KBr pellet (red stripes), the region between 2800-2950 cm^{-1} showed a difference. The peak intensity in the 850-950 cm^{-1} region was found to be more intense in the spectrum of the sample prepared with KBr. At 2300 cm^{-1} , no peak was observed in FTIR-ATR spectra, but it was observed in the sample prepared with KBr pellet. In the literature, derivative spectra have been used using the KBr pellet-FTIR technique for the estimation of the active ingredient entecavir monohydrate. Second-derivative peaks from the C=O stretching were used in the FTIR spectra. The technique was statistically compared with the pharmacopoeia method (HPLC), and the results demonstrated its applicability. It has been reported that this technique can be used as an alternative and that similar methods can be developed (Khanam et al., 2020).

4. Conclusions

The pharmaceutical and physicochemical properties of levothyroxine have important effects on the bioavailability and clinical efficacy of the drug. External factors such as pH and humidity can disrupt the molecular structure and reduce the effectiveness of the drug. In this study, second derivative spectra were found to be useful, although there is a possibility of excipient-induced peaks. In order to see the overlapping peaks more clearly, the Savitzky-Golay technique used for peak analysis made the peaks with low intensity

values visible. Current methods for quantitative analysis, such as HPLC, are expensive, laborious, time-consuming and require chemical reagents. Molecular spectroscopy applications are increasing in the determination of the composition of drugs. There is also a current focus on the development of non-destructive methods. Spectroscopic methods may not give all the information about the chemical composition of the sample and may not find its characteristic chemical markers. However, when combined with statistical methods such as chemometric methods, principal component analysis (PCA) or cluster analysis (CA), they become a more powerful analytical tool. In the future, this approach needs to be expanded to a larger scale by increasing the number and types of drugs. In the spectra, there may also be changes in the peaks related to the coating material of the tablets. The possibility of developing a quantitative and non-destructive method to investigate the effect of this situation on the quality of the drug can also be evaluated.

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